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PARENTS' CONCERNS ABOUT THE USE OF COMPUTER-BASED TESTING (CBT) FOR UTME IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

Science and Technology have obviously taken over the way things are being done globally. Computer-Based Testing (CBT) is a subset of learning technology which comprises basically the application of technology for the enhancement of teaching, learning and assessment. This study involves a sample of 533 (219 males and 314 females) respondents drawn from 18 Local Government Areas in Cross River State, using accidental sampling technique. Three research questions and two hypotheses were formulated for this study. A 30-item validated Computer-Based Testing Questionnaire (CBTQ) developed by the researcher was used in data collection. Data analyses were done using percentages and chi-square (X^2). It was found out that parents had an unfavourable disposition, with female parents showing higher disposition than male; and the greatest disposition, being found among parents with ND/B.sc. Among the recommendations, was that, prior to the full implementation of CBT, major parameters such as infrastructure, school readiness and pre-testing practice must be on ground.

Key words: Parents' concerns, computer-based testing, UTME.

Introduction

The Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) is conducted by the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) as the universal entrance examination for candidates wishing to study in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Before JAMB was established in 1978 following decree (Act) No.2 of 1978 and amended by Decree (Act) No.33 of 1981 and Decree (Act) No.4 of 1993, the system of admission into Nigerian universities was autonomous, with each university conducting its own entrance examination. This system became complicated and characterized by limitations including waste of resources in the administration of the concessional examinations, multiplicity of university entrance examinations, applications and admissions into the Nigerian tertiary institutions.

According to Aminu (2014), problems of tribalism, ethnicity and favoritism also became rampant in the admission process and paved way for a standardized method of enrolling students into Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education. UTME was therefore, established by JAMB in 2010 to promote egalitarian admission policy in our universities, and over the years, performed its functions in line with the provision of DECREE that brought it about (Idika, Ayang & Joshua, 2007). It has since inception, ensured uniform standards in the conduct of matriculation examinations and in the placement of suitably qualified candidates in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

In carrying out its role of conducting public exams, JAMB has over the years, administered the UTME simultaneously in one day as a paper-pencil examination in over three hundred and seventy towns in the country. The Paper-Pencil Test (PPT) involves the traditional use of paper and pencil delivery of tests for marking.

The challenges of the paper-pencil Test over the years brought its pressure to bear on the Board that was already over ladden with the weight of admission problems due largely to inadequate resources to match the unforeseen rise in student population (Ojerinde, 2014). The paper-pencil test involved:

1. Huge costs and excessive paper work in printing and distribution of examination materials (syllabuses, brochures, instructions and guidelines to invigilators and supervisors, question paper, etc).
2. The logistics of examination administration in terms of personnel, vehicles, monitors and security covers (- Police, Civil Defence, etc).
3. Poor infrastructure and inadequate facilities which do not satisfy the Board's specification.
4. The JAMB admission population problem has continued and heightened with this mode of exam delivery in spite of the increased number of universities lately, to 122. The Board revealed recently that 1million out of the 1.7million candidates in the country who sat for UTME in 2013 would not be eligible for admission (JAMB, 2014). With over 100 universities, the Federal Government claims that institutions are not enough to address the challenges currently facing the nation's tertiary education.

The problem of accessing admission into the nation's tertiary institutions is further accentuated by the over subscription of applicants to federal universities, because of its low and affordable tuition. Yet, an increase of 13.35% was recorded in the 2013 UTME figure over that of 2012. These challenges have led JAMB to evolve its examinations in various models, and the latest evolution of which is the Computer-Based Testing (CBT), now in use since 2013.

CBT, also known as Computer Based Assessment (CBA) or e-examination, is a method of administering tests in which the responses are electronically recorded and assessed (Ojerinde, 2014). According to Olawale and shafi'I (2010), CBT is the process by which examinations are delivered, taken and scored electronically. It entails questions being deployed onto computer works stations (intranet and internet) and candidates answering the question on to the computer. The process of writing examinations is thus completely paperless. This testing method is being extensively used in many parts of the world today.

More so, the CBT model has been designed in such a manner that any Nigerian child who can use mobile handset should be able to use the model to attempt any question using the computer. According to Ojerinde (2014), CBT is embraced as a positive change that will put the Nigerian child on the same pedestal with its counterparts abroad. This can be seen in the light of the fact that computers are now an established part of daily lives and their use in education has become widespread. Njoku (2006) noted that many students around the world today, have excellent keyboard skills and computer knowledge even from early age.

Educational testing or assessment is a critical aspect of educational system. The trend of testing in today's technological advanced world is geared towards bringing about development and up-grade in the conduct of public examinations. JAMB (2014) observed that the educational testing practices in Nigeria which have predominantly been paper – and – pencil may not prepare children to face global developments associated with the desired advancement in technology and education (JAMB, Press Pass 2014).

Ojerinde (2014) emphasized that with CBT, the following advantages are very possible in advancing the course of educational testing in Nigeria:

1. Increased delivery of test items that have been calibrated and delineated according to their pertinent item characteristic (instructional levels/objectives, difficulty level, discrimination level and functionality distracters),
2. Efficient administration of examination and scoring of tests.
3. Improved test security resulting from electronic transmission and encryption for total eradication of breaches of examination security.
4. Unbiased test administration and scoring,
5. Increased computer awareness.
6. Reduction in the spate of examination security breaches, issues of cancellation of result due to insecurity and missing results due to candidates carelessness will be eradicated and
7. Improving the quality and standard of education in the long run.

According to Lukeman and Ogechi (2012), the use of CBT simplifies the entire testing cycle, including generation, execution, evaluation and presentation of test. The authors noted that CBT advantages including the standardization of test administration condition, offer test developers the opportunity to improve their productivity and lead to innovation in their fields and that no matter the tests' population size, CBT helps developers to set the same test conditions for all participants.

Despite the well recognized and apparent advantages of CBT over the PPT, several concerns from different stakeholders particularly parents are being raised. Major concerns observed from the exploratory interviews of parents by the researcher, were generally on infrastructural backing in the society particularly in the area of electricity, computer knowledge, school readiness for the CBT assessment mode, parental income support, prompt release of results, and generally, computer penetration and access, as well as test security challenge arising from frequency of test administrations, among others.

In the study carried out on undergraduate students' concerns about the use of Computer Assisted Assessment (CAA) in University of Calabar. Asim and Idika (2011), concluded that students were not favourable to the use of CAA for either Assessment for learning (AFL) or Assessment of Learning (AOL). The study found out that students rather had genuine concerns about lack of computer/internet skills, teachers' supervisory control over the conduct of examinations, leakages of questions, students' ratio to available computer and poor electricity supply. The study revealed too that the above concerns were more strongly felt among the females (74%), than their male counterparts (26%) and that students from highly educated parents than those from parents with low educational background, showed unfavourable disposition to the use of CAA.

Similarly Uwakwe (2005) had earlier observed that tests can be biased in favour of the dominant social group. Several other studies (Burns & Bozema, 1981; Campbell, Peck, Horn & Leigh, 1987; Barrett & Lally, 1999; Mavarech & Rich, 1985; Etukudo & Utin, 2006) have elaborately been concluded both internationally and locally by researchers using computer assisted assessment (CAA), computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) in teaching, learning and assessment.

A dominant concern often expressed by parents and other stakeholders of computer based examination is the issue of computer knowledge/skills. A study carried out by Lukeman and Ogechi (2012), investigated the effect of test mode administration on the validity of computer – based testing (CBT) among 120 students of Universities of Nigeria, Nsukka and Ilorin where CBT was already in use. It was revealed that computer knowledge of students could influence their performance on

CBT either positively or negatively. In agreement, Ojerinde (2014) noted that candidates and parents have shown great enthusiasm with the CBT use as this was shown by the number of registered candidates for 2013 CBT which was more than the initial target of JAMB.

In consideration of the enormous challenges posed by the conventional paper – pencil delivery mode of JAMB UTME, the Board has considered the introduction of Computer-Based Testing (CBT) which is widely seen as a catalyst for change in this era of information technology. However, it appears that the use of CBT as an assessment method in UTME has not attracted much attention. The question is, will the shifting of assessment from non-digital paper and pencil type to the computer-aided test improve the UTME in Nigeria and end the age long problem of JAMB? It is with this in mind that the researcher sets to examine, from the parents' perspective, their acceptance or non-acceptance of CBT for UTME in Cross River State, Nigeria.

The main purpose of the study was to investigate parents' concerns about the use of computer-based testing (CBT) for UTME in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the investigator was interested in finding out:

1. If parents sampled were favourably or unfavourably disposed to a shift in testing delivery from the traditional paper and pencil type to the use of CBT.
2. If response pattern of parents would depend on their Gender and
3. Educational level.

To achieve these objectives, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. Do parents of UTME candidates have favourable/unfavourable disposition towards CBT use in examination?
2. What is the difference between male and female parents in their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination?
3. Is there any influence of parental educational level of parents on their disposition towards CBT use in examination?
The two hypotheses that were tested are:
4. There is no significant difference between male and female parents of JAMB UTME candidates in their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.
5. There is no significant influence of educational level of parents on their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

Method

The study used a survey of the ex-post-facto nature. This design was adopted because the researcher did not manipulate the variables but studied their outcomes as

observed among the sample studied (Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim & Ekuri, 2004). The population of this study consisted of all parents/guardians of candidates of 2014 JAMB UTME which took place between May 17th and 31st 2014 in two designated centers – e-library University of Calabar and computer science department software unit, Cross River University of Technology. The population of 5,359 was found in the 18 Local Government Areas of Cross River State, representing the total no of parents on JAMB roll as parents of UTME candidates for 2014.

219 male and 314 female parents of UTME candidates were accidentally selected continuously until 533 copies of the questionnaire were administered as the sample for the study. The need to use the accidental sampling became urgent as these parents could only be reached to get their opinion on the use of CBT at the centers of examination where they gathered to drop, wait or pick their children/wards after examination.

A 30-item questionnaire, called Computer-Based Testing Questionnaire (CBTQ) was the instrument used for data collection. Ten items were also selected from the 30 items in the questionnaire as the major concern to test the favourable/unfavourable disposition of parents in the use of CBT in examination. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part sought information about UTME candidates' parents' demographic variables while the second part of the questionnaire focused on the disposition or concerns of parents of UTME candidates towards the use of CBT for examination.

In order to ascertain the validity of the CBTQ scale, items were generated from prior exploratory interviews across groups of some parents of UTME candidates during various interactions in formal and informal settings. Only concerns shared by over 50% of such parents were included as questionnaire items. To further ascertain the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was referred to experts in the field of Measurement in Education for vetting so as to ensure its appropriateness, relevance and clarity. To ascertain the reliability of the CBTQ instrument, the Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the consistency. The analysis yielded the reliability index of 0.69.

Five hundred and thirty six (536) copies of the CBT questionnaire were administered to selected sample through contact persons in the 2 UTME centers covering the 18 Local Government Areas of Cross River State, over a period of the two weeks, (17th -31st May, 2014) UTME examination. The researcher was assisted by four research assistants in the administration of the questionnaire. Out of this number, (533) were retrieved giving a return rate of 99.4 percent.

On the issue of whether parents of UTME candidates were favourably or unfavourably disposed to the use of CBT, the researcher considered parent concerns or views

in terms of the use of CBT for purpose of replacing paper and pencil UTME. Parents were to indicate their responses and these were regrouped into favourable and unfavourable responses based on the "yes/no" response. Every unfavourable response was an indication that parents were against the use of CBT while a favourable response shows, that they were in support of CBT use in examination.

Results

Research Question

Do parents of UTME candidates have favourable/unfavourable disposition towards the use of CBT in examination?

Table 1

Percentage analysis of parents of UTME candidates' disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

s/n	Parents' Perception of CBT in JAMB UTME	Disposition Unfavourable	Favourable	Total
1	Electricity interruption may affect children's performance.	436 (81.8%)	97 (18.2%)	533
2	Candidates who cannot use the computer will fail.	474 (88.9%)	59 (11.1%)	533
3	It will make a child's score to be given to him/her immediately after the examination.	73 (13.7%)	460 (86.3%)	533
4	Candidates will exchange information during the exam.	305 (57.2%)	228 (42.8%)	533
5	If candidates are too many, they cannot all write the exam at the same venue and anything can happen at different venues.	392 (73.5%)	141 (26.5%)	533
6	The Nigerian society and our environment cannot be judged to be ripe for any CBT.	326 (61.2%)	207 (38.8%)	533
7	If the computer develops a problem, time for examination will finish without a candidate attempting all questions.	297 (55.7%)	236 (44.3%)	533
8	If a candidate fails, it may not be easy to know whether he/she lacks knowledge or because of faults from the computer.	253 (47.5%)	280 (52.5%)	533
9	It is very possible that many children have never had access to computer before.	484 (90.8%)	49 (9.2%)	533
10	Buying computer for home use should be a secondary issue.	302 (56.7%)	231 (43.3%)	533
	Total	334.2	198.8	
	Average	334.2	198.8	
	Percentage	62.7%	37.3%	

Analysis was done using percentages to find out if the parents sampled, were favourable or unfavourable in their disposition towards the use of CBT in the examination. The result, as shown in the table 1 above, indicated that 334.2 (62.7%) were unfavourable towards the use of CBT while 198.8 (37.3%) were favourable.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference between male and female parents in their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination

Table 2

Chi-square analysis showing male and female parents in their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

	Disposition	Gender		Total
		Male	female	
	Low	51	88	139
	medium	147	138	285
	High	21	88	109
	Total	209	314	533

$P < .05$, $df=1$, Critical $X^2=3.84$, $X^2 = 35.51$

The result above shows that the calculated X^2 of 35.51 is greater than the critical X^2 value of 3.84 at .05 level of significance, with degree of freedom of 1, which supports the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, an alternative hypothesis was established which shows that there is a significant difference between male and female parents in their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant influence of educational level of parents of UTME candidates on their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

Table 3

Chi-square analysis showing educational level of parents of UTME candidates and their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination

	Disposition	Parental Educational Level				Total
		FSLC	JSS/SSCE	BSC/NDC	M.ED/PHD	
139	Low	9	5	125	0	139
285	medium	9	69	136	71	285
109	High	1	3	44	61	109
533	Total	19	77	305	132	533

$P < .05$, $df=6$, critical $x^2 = 12.59$, $x^2 = 159.186$

The above analysis shows that the calculated X^2 value of 159.186 is greater than the critical X^2 value of 12.59 at .05 level of significance with degree of freedom as 6, which supports the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, an alternate hypothesis was established: there is significant influence of educational level of parents on their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

Discussion of findings

The results of the study in research question (table 1) revealed that, generally, the parents of UTME candidates were unfavourable to the use of CBT. That is 337.2 (62.7%) were unfavourable towards the use of CBT while 198.8 (37.3%) were favourably disposed towards the use of CBT. Availability of infrastructure, readiness for CBT assessment mode, computer knowledge and skills, prompt release of results and parental income support were the major concerns being measured. The results showed that, the parents of UTME candidates were unfavourable to the use of CBT. This is supported by Wasanga and Wanderi (2005), whose findings confirmed availability of infrastructure as the basic requirement for on-line assessment.

Hypothesis one (table 2)

The results of the study in hypothesis one (table 2) revealed that male and female parents significantly differ in their disposition towards the use of CBT in examination. That is, calculated X^2 value of 35.51 is greater than the critical X^2 value of 3.84 at .05 level of significance which supports the rejection of H_{01} . Prior to this study, various studies have equally confirmed gender difference in learning styles (Serveriens (1995) and Meyer et al (1995). These studies observed that when using computers, females have been considered to possess a higher level of computer anxiety than males and to experience more negative feelings towards computers. In contrast, Stephens (2000), observed that there are no apparent disadvantages to female students when delivering tests using computer assessment.

The results of the study in table 3 revealed that parental educational level significantly influenced parents' disposition towards the use of CBT in examination.

Conclusion

The study sought to examine parents of UTME candidates' disposition towards the use of CBT in Cross River State. The major concerns measured, were availability of infrastructure, readiness for CBT assessment mode, computer knowledge and skills, prompt release of results and parental income support. With respect to the results of the findings of this study, it is concluded that the disposition of parents of UTME candidates was unfavourable to the use CBT for examination. The male and female parents were different in their disposition towards the use of

CBT for examination. Parental educational level of parents of UTME candidates also influenced their disposition towards the use of CBT for examination. The overall parents' disposition is that emergence of CBT in UTME in Cross River State and in Nigeria, if given adequate infrastructural and other supports, is a welcomed strategy not only for enhancing JAMB efficiency in conducting credible and fair public examination, but ICT skills, thereby hastening the nation's movement with the global train.

Recommendation

1. Before the full implementation of CBT in 2015 as proposed by JAMB, governments, private and various stakeholders in the educational sector should ensure that technically capable facilities for CBT centres are in place.
2. Effective periodic inspection of the schools' readiness for CBT assessment mode should be carried out by the ministry of education.
3. Practice testing to enable students overcome computer anxiety and training and retraining of personnel for the success of CBT.

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